

IEA Wind Task 52: Nacelle Mounted Lidar in Complex Terrain Sub-group – Simple+ Whitepaper

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1 Introduction

This white paper defines a supplemental uncertainty framework for the use of nacelle-mounted lidar (NML) for wind turbine power performance testing (PPT) in moderately complex terrain. It is an incremental expansion from the existing international standard, IEC 61400-50-3 (50-3). The 50-3 explicitly restricts the use of NML to simple (flat) terrain, as defined in the IEC 61400-12-5 (12-5) standard, although the current edition of 50-3 still refers to the identical definition contained in IEC 61400-12-1:2017 (12-1). It has been demonstrated that nacelle lidars reduce the Category A uncertainty of PPTs when compared to simultaneous PPTs carried out with co-located met masts. One of the origins of this improvement is the alignment of the NML beams with the turbine's yaw orientation; met masts are only aligned in a narrow wind direction sector. In this whitepaper, we introduce a framework called "Simple+" Terrain, where the observed NML improvements in uncertainty justify relaxation of the terrain restrictions on NML usage. The uncertainties associated with loosening terrain restrictions are described quantitatively in this whitepaper. The derivations here build on the analytical toolkit in 50-3, including white box uncertainty propagation, and uncertainties associated with measurement height errors. The overall goal is to balance the reductions in NML uncertainty with the increases in terrain relaxation uncertainty such that the overall uncertainty of an NML PPT measuring between 2 and 3 rotor diameters (D) in Simple+ terrain is the same as the uncertainty of a met mast PPT in flat terrain measuring between 2 and 4 D.

This white paper was developed by representatives from turbine OEMs, wind farm developers, independent engineering firms, lidar OEMs, and wind energy academic researchers and reflects the positions of the individual co-authors. This document represents an industry consensus on practical NML uncertainty treatments in moderately complex terrain. The group met regularly throughout 2024 and 2025 to develop the ideas, draft sub-sections, and to learn about nacelle lidar in complex terrain from various group members and world experts. These meetings were facilitated by the International Energy Agency Wind Task 52: *Large-scale Deployment of Wind Lidar*, but the document has not undergone review by the full IEA Wind Task 52 committee.

2 Pre-Campaign and Campaign Computations

In the Simple+ PPT use case, there are two distinct phases with different uncertainty computations. The first phase is before the PPT (hereafter "pre-campaign"). The purpose of this pre-campaign computation is to determine whether the site is Simple+ within acceptable uncertainties. This assessment is performed using data gathered during the wind resource assessment (WRA) measurement campaign and digital elevation models (DEM) or other on-site survey data. Note that pre-campaign computations do not constitute PPT uncertainties, but rather the input for the decision to use NML or mast-mounted anemometry for the PPT. The necessary computations to make this decision transparently are included in this white paper.

The second phase is during the PPT, for which the pre-campaign analysis concluded that the site was Simple+ and so the PPT is carried out using an NML. This phase uses data measured by the NML, corrected, if necessary, using the DEM. This white paper contains guidance on how to estimate uncertainties of the measured and adjusted wind speeds. These uncertainties are used directly in the PPT. The techniques described follow best practices of white-box uncertainty propagation. The wind shear and wind speeds measured by the NML, as well as the exact details of the installed wind turbine, are used as inputs.

3 Justification of Simple+ Uncertainty Budget

Studies comparing simultaneous wind measurements from industry accepted nacelle mounted lidars and met masts have shown lower Category A power curve measurement uncertainties for nacelle mounted lidars in simple terrain (*Feeney et al (2014)*, *Wagner et al (2015)*, and *Liang, Z. (2024)*). The hypothesized origin of this reduction in uncertainty is the NML's alignment with the turbine's upwind flow in all wind direction sectors.

Section E.9 of IEC 61400-12-1:2022, provides the recommended terrain uncertainty range for simple terrain sites. For measurements between 2 and 3 rotor diameters, the IEC default uncertainty is 2%, and between 3 and 4 rotor diameters the uncertainty is 3%. In this document, we compare this 2%-3% estimate with estimates of uncertainties associated with (1) terrain slope and (2) terrain deviations from a plane. The 2%-3% range aligns well with the uncertainties predicted for (1) and (2) within the simple terrain limits. The Simple+ terrain concept relaxes the IEC 50-3 simple terrain criteria, employing slightly steeper slopes and slightly taller deviations from a plane by using the IEC default 3% terrain uncertainty for measurements between 2 and 3 rotor diameters and thus allowing a 1% Simple+ error budget. This additional terrain uncertainty is partially offset by the NML's reduced Category A uncertainty. Additionally, the use of lidar point cloud DEMs, presented in this document, further reduces terrain-associated uncertainty.

This overall Simple+ budget is set non-dimensionally as a proportion (percentage/100) but is sometimes converted to m/s for computations. Both proportion and m/s are used in this document for combining uncertainties and demonstrating the relative sizes of the proposed uncertainties.

The Simple+ toolkit allows for more sites to employ NML that will reduce overall testing costs and allow for testing at locations where land restrictions make it difficult to install a mast.

4 Calculating Hills and Obstacles Uncertainties

4.1 Evaluating site for Simple+ criteria

This section describes the process to determine if a site can be classified as Simple+. For ordinary 50-3 NML PPTs, terrain is classified as Simple or Complex similar to Table 3 from 12-5:

Distance	Sector	Maximum slope	Maximum terrain variation from a plane
<2L	360°	<3	< 1/3 (H – 0.5 D)
≥2L and < 4L	Measurement sector	<5	< 2/3 (H – 0.5 D)
≥2L and < 4L	Outside measurement sector	<10*	Not applicable
≥4L and < 8L	Measurement sector	<10	< (H – 0.5 D)
≥8L and < 16L	Measurement sector	<10*	Not applicable

Table 4-1: Test site Requirements: topographical variations from 12-5

Where:

H is the proposed turbine hub height

D is the proposed turbine rotor diameter

L is the distance between lidar wind measurement point and the turbine base

Sector is an individual non-overlapping 30° sector, free from major obstacles

Maximum slope is the slope of the best-fit plane including the tower base and measurement sector. Where marked (*) the slope is that of the steepest line connecting the tower base and points in the sector

If the *Maximum slope* (slope) or *Maximum terrain variation from a plane* (terrain variation) exceeds the values in Table 4-1, the site is classified as Complex. In this case, 12-1 requires that a site calibration is done for the PPT using a met mast. Currently, NML PPTs are restricted to only simple terrain by the 50-3. In this section, we expand the test site slope and terrain variation requirements to provide a framework for NML in Simple+ terrain.

Figure 4-1: Illustration of areas to be assessed

The first step in evaluating the site is to assess which wind direction sectors are Simple. Follow the terrain evaluation procedure in the 12-5. Table 4-1 shows the Simple terrain limits on terrain slope and obstacle height from the 12-5. Figure 4-1 shows the key regions of interest for the evaluation of a single wind direction sector. The calculations of Simple terrain limits are repeated for each 30° wind sector. The slope and terrain variation are illustrated in Figure 4-2. Note that the wind turbine location and measurement location are distinct locations, and it may be necessary to repeat the computation for the turbine location and the NML measurement point 2-3 D upwind in each direction sector (50-3 10.4.3). It is likely that the site assessment conclusion on Simple, Simple+, and Complex terrain will be similar between the two locations. The Simple+ concept provides a toolbox for these slightly complex terrain edge cases, where the existing standard is inflexible. The alignment of the wind measurement with the wind turbine inflow is a key advantage compared to a met mast PPT.

Figure 4-2: Example of determination of terrain variation from the best-fit plane: “2L to 4L” and the case “measurement sector” from 12-5

If all sectors are classified as Simple, NML PPT is permitted by the 50-3 standard. If some sectors exceed the limits in Table 4-1, it may still be possible to carry out a Simple terrain PPT by excluding sectors outside the limits. Sector management may become impractical as the number of non-Simple sectors increases. This common scenario is where it is recommended to more finely classify sectors as Simple+ or Complex.

4.1.1 Simple+ Equivalent limits

The derivation to arrive at the equivalent limits from Table 4-1 uses equations defined in 50-3 A.4 *Uncertainty contributions from variation of measurement height*. The following definitions are employed in the derivation to arrive at the final solution. Full derivation is in Appendix 10.1.

- V_m , the average annual wind speed at the site
- ΔV_{hor} , change in horizontal wind speed
- $B_{ms^{-1}}$, the Simple+ error budget, as a wind speed range

$$B_{ms^{-1}} \equiv u_{\Delta V, measHeight} = \frac{\Delta V_{hor}}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$$B_{ms^{-1}} \cdot \sqrt{3} = \Delta V_{hor}$$

- $B_{\%}$, the Simple+ error budget as a proportion
 - Not to exceed 1% (0.01) for slope or terrain variation alone;
 - Not to exceed 0.707% (0.00707) for both terrain variation and obstacles.
 - $B_{\%} = \frac{B_{ms^{-1}}}{V_m}$
- α , representative wind shear at the site (see Section 4.2)
- S , safety factor applied to measured wind shear
 - Recommend 10% (0.1)
 - Entered as $\alpha \cdot (1 + S) = 1.1\alpha$
- H , hub height

Simple+ equivalency for terrain variation (TV) is outlined in the following equation (see Appendix 10.1)

$$\Delta z_{Simple+,TV} = H \left(1 - \frac{1}{(B_{\%} \cdot \sqrt{3} + 1)^{\frac{1}{\alpha(1+S)}}} \right) + \Delta z_{Simple,TV}$$

Equation 1: Simple+ limits for Maximum terrain variation from a plane

The computed $\Delta z_{Simple+,TV}$ represents the terrain variation height permitted for a Simple+ sector.

Example:

For a site with hub height, $H = 100$ m and rotor diameter, $D = 100$ m, the permitted terrain variation for Simple terrain is:

$$\Delta z_{Simple,TV} = \frac{1}{3} * (H - 0.5 * D) = 16.7 \text{ m}$$

For the same site, with wind shear, $\alpha = 0.2$, 10% safety factor, and $B = 1\%$ Simple+ budget:

$$\Delta Z_{Simple+,TV} = 100 \left(1 - \frac{1}{(0.01 \cdot \sqrt{3} + 1)^{\frac{1}{0.2(1+0.1)}}} \right) + 16.7 = 24.2 \text{ m}$$

This represents an additional terrain variation allowance of 7.5 m.

The basis of the terrain variation Simple+ allowance is the strong likelihood that the terrain variation has modified the measurement height of the lidar beam above ground level. Simple+ strongly assumes terrain-following wind flow vectors. The equation above relates the uncertainty budget to the change in wind speed due to the wind shear and terrain variation, and converts this to the new, Simple+ terrain variation budget.

For slope (m), the methodology is multi-step and begins with height difference from the permitted slope for Simple terrain for the specific site (ex. $L = 2.5D = 250 \text{ m}$ and an allowed slope of 3%):

$$\Delta Z_{Simple,m} = \left(1 + \frac{m}{100} \right) * 2L - 2L = 15 \text{ meters}$$

Compute the variation in wind speed due to the terrain slope and wind shear:

$$\Delta V_{hor} = V_m * \left[\left(\frac{H + \Delta Z_{Simple,m}}{H} \right)^\alpha - 1 \right]$$

In Simple+ terrain, terrain slope measurement height errors are corrected using a DEM. The residual wind speed uncertainty after correcting for the measurement height is:

$$u_{\Delta V} = \frac{\Delta V_{hor}}{2\sqrt{3}}$$

Convert to a proportion:

$$u_{\Delta V,\%} = \frac{u_{\Delta V}}{V_m}$$

Note that the factor V drops out of the entire computation here as V is in the numerator and denominator. Next, add the Simple+ uncertainty budget:

$$u_{\Delta V,\%,Simple+} = u_{\Delta V,\%} + B_{\%}$$

Convert back to wind speed and remultiply by the reduction factor:

$$\Delta V_{Simple+,m} = u_{\Delta V,\%,Simple+} * V_m * 2\sqrt{3}$$

Convert this wind speed deviation to an elevation difference:

$$\Delta Z_{Simple+,m} = H * \left(\frac{\Delta V_{Simple+,m}}{V} + 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - H$$

Finally, convert this to a slope:

$$m_{Simple+} = \frac{\Delta Z_{Simple+,m}}{2L}$$

This computation is repeated for 2L, 4L, 8L, and 16L.

Example:

For Simple terrain limits, the Maximum slope is fixed at 3, 5, 10, and 10 for 2L, 4L, 8L, and 16L.

For Simple+ with $H = 100\text{ m}$, $D = 100\text{m}$, $\alpha = 0.2$, $S = 10\%$ safety factor, and $B_{\%} = 1\%$ Simple+ budget following the computations above:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m_{Simple+,2L} &= 7.1\% \\
 m_{Simple+,4L} &= 7.6\% \\
 m_{Simple+,4L,out} &= 13.2\% \\
 m_{Simple+,8L} &= 12.2\% \\
 m_{Simple+,16L} &= 11.6\%
 \end{aligned}$$

These represent increases of 4.1%, 2.6%, 3.2%, 2.2%, 1.6% compared to Simple terrain.

The Microsoft Excel workbook *IEATask52_NMLX_SimplePlusWorkbook.xlsx* computes these uncertainties based on user input, and include example calculations for certain key scenarios:

- Simple terrain
- Simple+ budget spent on terrain variation ($B_{\%} = 1\%$ (0.01))
- Simple+ budget spent on slope ($B_{\%} = 1\%$ (0.01))
- Simple+ budget split evenly between terrain variation and slope ($B_{\%} = 0.707\%$ (0.00707))

The even-split case is a useful tool for rapid evaluation of wind sectors. The final values for terrain variation and slope vary depending on turbine hub height, rotor diameter, and wind shear. The wind speed does not affect the final values and could be dropped from the derivation, but it is useful to illustrate the logical steps developed by the IEA Wind Task 52 working group.

4.2 Representative Wind Shear

Wind shear can exhibit strong diurnal and seasonal variance. In Simple+ terrain, where local, terrain-induced flows may exist, there could be correlations between wind shear and wind direction. Furthermore, wind shear may vary with wind speed. Since PPT are carried out with specific uncertainty in each wind speed bin, the contribution of wind shear to the overall uncertainty of a PPT may have significant variation over wind speed. To avoid an excess of new uncertainties in any wind speed bin, an evaluation of wind shear should be carried out to derive these variations and determine a representative wind shear for various site conditions. The representative wind shear should not be less than 0.15.

Input Parameters	Value
Budget	0.00707
Shear	0.15
Hub height (H)	100 m
Wind speed	7.5 m/s
Safety factor	0.1
L (2.5D for NML)	200 m
Rotor diameter (D)	80 m

Table 4-2: Lower bound (0.15) example input parameters

Simple+ Slope	Simple+ Obstacle Height
7.8%	27.1
7.9%	47.1
13.6%	NA
12.4%	67.1
11.8%	NA

Table 4-3: Simple+ slope and obstacle limits

Using the data gathered during the WRA campaign, compute and record the wind shear in each direction, and for each wind speed bin. Using the measured annual wind rose, it is possible to identify risks of excessive uncertainty if the prevailing wind direction coincides with high wind shear. Furthermore, if the prevailing wind during the PPT campaign is not coincident with the expected wind direction, those uncertainties can be easily identified and sector management used to maintain the expected uncertainty budget of the Simple+ PPT.

4.3 Derivation of Terrain uncertainty for Simple+

For the NML campaign, these uncertainties are computed using the NML-measured wind speeds and an appropriate DEM. Those uncertainties are propagated through the Wind Field Reconstruction algorithm following the 50-3 white box approach.

Changes in elevation between the sampling points of the NML and the hub height result in biases in mean wind speed and direction due to the presence of wind shear. Within the Simple+ limits, one can assume that the shear profile is simply shifted based on the local terrain elevation. In other words, the gentle terrain slopes do not cause significant distortion of the undisturbed shear profile. This simplification enables a simple calculation of the bias on the reconstructed wind vector seen by the NML as a function of the nacelle orientation and focal distance.

4.3.1 Systematic Errors Due to Elevation Differences and Wind Shear

We consider the case of a two-beam NML shown in Figure 4-3: Definitions relevant for the two-beam lidar case study. Figure 4-3 (the general case of a multi-beam NML can be easily derived similarly).

Figure 4-3: Definitions relevant for the two-beam lidar case study.

For an ideal lidar with negligible probe volume, the line-of-sight velocities can be expressed as:

$$V_{r,1} = V_H \left(\frac{Z_1}{Z_H} \right)^\alpha \cos(\gamma - \theta) \cos(\phi)$$

$$V_{r,2} = V_H \left(\frac{Z_2}{Z_H} \right)^\alpha \cos(\gamma + \theta) \cos(\phi)$$

Note that the yaw misalignment θ is assumed to be constant with height, meaning that we neglect wind veer.

Figure 4-4: Bias on the reconstructed horizontal wind speed induced by terrain elevation difference for zero yaw misalignment and tilt.

Figure 4-5: Bias on the reconstructed horizontal wind direction induced by terrain elevation difference for zero yaw misalignment and tilt.

Where α is the shear exponent, assumed to be constant in space. For two-beam NML, a simple wind reconstruction in the Cartesian turbine frame of reference is:

$$V_{x,rec} = \frac{V_{r,1} + V_{r,2}}{2 \cos(\phi) \cos(\gamma)}$$

$$V_{y,rec} = \frac{V_{r,1} - V_{r,2}}{2 \sin(\phi) \cos(\gamma)}$$

Thus:

$$V_{H,rec} = \sqrt{V_{x,rec}^2 + V_{y,rec}^2}$$

$$\theta_{rec} = \arctan\left(\frac{V_{y,rec}}{V_{x,rec}}\right)$$

Figure 4-4 and Figure 4-5 show the errors in wind speed and wind direction due to height differences between the two lidar measurement points and the turbine hub height. If no correction is applied to the lidar data, these represent direct estimates of uncertainties originating in systematic errors in the wind field reconstruction (WFR).

4.3.2 Estimating Residual Errors When Applying Corrections to NML Data

The 50-3 advises applying corrections to the NML-measured wind speeds using the wind shear at the lidar measurement points to interpolate or extrapolate the measured speeds to turbine hub height. This adjustment includes two sources of data: the DEM used to estimate the height of lidar measurement point, and the estimate of wind shear used to interpolate or extrapolate the data. These two data sources have associated uncertainties. When using a DEM and NML-measured wind shear to correct the data, there will be a residual error in the final estimate of hub height wind speed. To estimate the residual error, one may add the wind shear and DEM uncertainties to the WFR algorithm as a Gaussian random error drawn from a distribution with standard deviation equal to the uncertainty associated with shear or the DEM. Following a simple Monte Carlo uncertainty approach, the two-beam NML WFR calculation is repeated, generating a distribution of errors as its output. The standard deviation of the error distribution represents the uncertainty associated with wind shear uncertainty, DEM uncertainty, or both. The two new uncertainties may be added to WFR algorithm:

$$V_{r,1} = V_H \left(\frac{Z_1 + \Delta Z_1}{Z_H} \right)^{\alpha_1 + \Delta \alpha_1} \cos(\gamma - \theta) \cos(\phi)$$

$$V_{r,2} = V_H \left(\frac{Z_2 + \Delta Z_2}{Z_H} \right)^{\alpha_2 + \Delta \alpha_2} \cos(\gamma + \theta) \cos(\phi)$$

Note that it is not necessary to apply the corrections numerically in this approach. The corrections are represented by the mean errors as shown in Figure 4-6 and Figure 4-7. Our interest is the standard deviation of the error, which is unchanged when applying the correction.

The Δz terrain uncertainty term is documented in the DEM used for evaluating the terrain and is discussed in *Calculating Elevation Difference Uncertainties*. The $\Delta \alpha$ shear uncertainty term is derived from the wind measurements and methods for uncertainty estimation are described in detail in CDV 61400-15-2 Appendix A. The input configuration to the Monte Carlo model is described in Table 4-4.

Variable	Values
Wind shear	-0.05, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3
Wind shear uncertainty	0, 0.07, 0.1, 0.5
Elevation offset (m)	-25, -15, -5, 5, 15, 25
Elevation uncertainty (m)	0, 0.1, 1, 2, 4
Correlation between errors	0, 0.5, 1.0
Number of runs each configuration	100
Wind speed (m/s)	10
Hub height (m)	100

Note: no uncertainties applied directly to wind speed or lidar tilt and roll angles

Table 4-4: Input variables to Monte Carlo uncertainty estimation for nacelle-mounted lidar in Simple+ terrain

Wind shear and elevation uncertainties are drawn from Gaussian distribution using Python’s NumPy package (function: random.multivariate_normal). Correlated random errors are specified using an input covariance matrix. Covariance between the random errors is necessary to understand as the elevation estimates may use the same or neighboring DEM points, which may exhibit covariance due to the instrument used in the DEM mission. Similarly, random errors in the upper and lower wind speed measurements from the nacelle lidar (used to calculate wind shear) may be correlated. Results generated with perfect correlation between random errors have slightly higher uncertainties than uncorrelated or partially correlated errors. Perfect correlation is used here as a conservative approach.

Figure 4-6: Standard deviation of residual error in two-beam NML compared to hub height wind speed, as a function of LOS height offsets and wind shear for low uncertainty DEM (0.1 m)

Figure 4-7: Standard deviation of residual error in two-beam NML compared to hub height wind speed, as a function of LOS height offsets and wind shear for high uncertainty DEM (4 m)

Shear	$\Delta Z_{max} [m]$	$\sigma_{HWS,max} [\%]$ $(u_{DEM}, u_{\alpha}) = (0.1 \text{ m}, 0.1)$	$\sigma_{HWS,max} [\%]$ $(u_{DEM}, u_{\alpha}) = (4 \text{ m}, 0.1)$	NML-X Workbook Estimates Terrain Slope only
-0.05	30	0.19	0.35	0.4
0.05	30	0.18	0.35	0.4
0.1	30	0.35	0.7	0.8
0.2	10	0.22	1.01	0.6
	20	0.40	1.04	1.1
	30	0.70	1.25	1.6
0.3	10	0.32	1.53	0.8
	20	0.61	1.65	1.6
	30	1.13	1.83	2.4
0.4	10	0.39	2.00	1.1
	20	0.89	2.00	2.2
	30	2.00	2.30	3.2

Table 4-5: Maximum wind speed uncertainties for various LOS height errors, DEM uncertainties, shear uncertainties, and wind shear. Note that for Simple terrain, for $D=100 \text{ m}$ (15 m of slope variation allowed), following the 12-1 and 50-3, u_{VT} is equal to 2%. Even for larger D , u_{VT} is fixed at 2%.

Table 4-5 shows the maximum wind speed uncertainty values from each panel for various ΔZ_{LOS} isolines. These uncertainties may be used conservatively for LOS elevations less than the ΔZ_{LOS} indicated in the table. These represent new uncertainties which can be added to a PPT for Simple+ terrain sites. See Section 6 Integrating Simple+ Uncertainties for more detail.

5 Digital Elevation Model (DEM) Uncertainties

To determine the appropriate vertical resolution uncertainty for a DEM in a lidar simulation, refer to the documentation of the individual satellite or lidar point cloud DEM used to estimate the local elevation around the wind project site. These documents for LPCs are listed in the Appendix and References. This section describes uncertainties of widely used satellite radar DEMs and the typical lidar DEM specifications.

5.1 Satellite radar DEMs

Satellite radar digital elevation models include the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) later improved in the NASADEM project. The TanDEM-X mission generated Copernicus' GLO-30 DEM. Alternative spaceborne DEMs include the Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER). Simard et al (2024) examines the uncertainty of these DEMs, comparing their elevation measurements to lidar measurements from various other mapping missions.

Reference	DEM	Mean bias (m)	Mean RMSE (m)
ICESat	SRTM v3	0.68	2.50
	NASADEM	0.00	1.50
	GLO-30	0.05	0.55
ICESat-2	SRTM v3	0.54	2.60
	NASADEM	0.01	1.60
	GLO-30	0.07	0.69
GEDI	SRTM v3	0.94	2.67
	NASADEM	0.06	1.81
	GLO-30	0.15	0.92

Table 5-1: Reproduced from Simard et al (2024). Estimated bias and uncertainties of various satellite radar DEMs

An earlier study from JPL, Rodriguez et al (2006), looks at a comparison between SRTM (v1) and ground-based kinematic GPS measurements from specially equipped vehicles on well-known roads. Earlier SRTM versions had fewer corrections and quality control applied to the data. This comparison

Continent	DEM	Mean bias (m)	Std dev (m)
Africa	SRTM	1.3	3.8
Australia	SRTM	1.8	3.5
Eurasia	SRTM	-0.7	3.7
New Zealand	SRTM	1.4	4.0
North America	SRTM	0.1	5.9
South America	SRTM	1.7	4.1

Table 5-2: Reproduced from Rodriguez et al (2006). Estimated bias and standard deviation of SRTM DEM for various continents

5.2 Lidar Point Cloud DEMs

Lidar point-cloud DEMs, such as those mentioned above use aircraft or satellite lidar to map elevation. A notable improvement in lidar terrestrial mapping is the ability of the lidar to penetrate and classify vegetation, greatly improving accuracy. The United States Geological Survey publishes annual base standards for DEMs generated using airborne lidar. These include a description of absolute vertical accuracy for lidar of various quality levels. More detail on each individual LPC DEM is included in the links in the Appendix 10.2.

Quality level	RMSE _v (nonvegetated) (m)
QL0	≤0.050
QL1	≤0.100
QL2	≤0.100
QL3	≤0.200

Table 5-3: Reproduced from USGS base standards for lidar-based DEMs. RMSE and associated quality level classification scheme.

6 Integrating Simple+ Uncertainties to PPTs

Uncertainties are combined explicitly by their inclusion in the WFR uncertainty estimation. The new uncertainties described in this document, those associated with DEMs and wind shear, are treated as independent Gaussian random variable. Their covariance is modeled in the Monte Carlo simulations included in this report. The relevant, associated uncertainties in the 12-1 and 50-3 are described below and some of the key methods are duplicated for reference.

6.1 IEC 61400-50-3

50-3 Section 9.4 *Uncertainty due to varying measurement height* introduces $u_{\langle\Delta V\rangle, measHeight}$. Further detail is included in 50-3 Section 11.8 *Measurement height variations*:

It is required to consider variations in the elevation of the nacelle lidar beams above ground or sea level during the measurements....

If the difference in terrain elevation across the measurement sector exceeds the limits given by the use case, the error in wind speed should be corrected for, either directly in the WFR algorithm or on the 10-min average reconstructed wind speed. The correction method shall be documented and an additional uncertainty term should be applied according to 9.4. If the requirements of the use case are met in a part of the measurement sector, the measurement sector can be adjusted to fulfil the measurement height requirements. See also 10.4.

Simple+ is explicitly a scenario where the terrain elevation differences exceed the limits of the use case. The tools in this whitepaper constitute an example of the necessary type of correction method to derive detailed $u_{\langle\Delta V\rangle, measHeight}$ uncertainties. Finally, the 50-3 Section A.4 *Uncertainty contributions from variation of measurement height* includes the following uncertainty for uncorrected measurement height errors.

$$u_{\langle\Delta V\rangle, measHeight} = \frac{\Delta V_{hor}}{\sqrt{3}}$$

This uncertainty term is for uncorrected measurement height variations. In cases where there are variations from a plane in a particular sector (see Figure 4-2 and 12-5 for variation computation technique), they should be documented for each sector, recorded in meters, and the associated uncertainties computed.

6.2 IEC 61400-12-1

The 12-1 introduces relevant uncertainty terms in 12-1 Section 6.3.4 *Correction factors and uncertainty due to flow distortion originating from topography*:

The test site shall be assessed for sources of wind flow distortion due to topographical variations. The assessment in Annex B shall identify whether the power curve can be measured without a site calibration. If the criteria of Annex B are met, the wind flow regime of the site does not need a site calibration. However, in assuming that no flow correction is necessary, the applied uncertainty due to flow distortion of the test site

shall be a minimum of 2 % of the measured wind speed if the wind measurement equipment is positioned at a distance between 2 and 3 times the rotor diameter of the wind turbine and 3 % or greater if the distance is between 3 and 4 times the rotor diameter, unless objective evidence can be provided quantifying a different uncertainty.

Following the Simple+ terrain concept, a flow correction is applied using shear interpolation and high quality DEMs. Simple+ strongly assumes terrain-following wind vectors. It is not intended for sites with more complex flow features. Finally, in 12-1 Section E.9 Category B uncertainties: Wind speed – Terrain, another relevant uncertainty is $u_{VT,i}$ a Category B uncertainty associated with Simple terrain where a site calibration is not performed. This is the case in Simple+ terrain, and this term should be retained. The addition of new measurement height uncertainties, and the reduction of Category A uncertainty due to the NML's alignment with the flow, the overall uncertainty budget of an NML campaign in Simple+ terrain will be within the 2%-3% uncertainty budget proposed in the 50-3.

When the power performance test is done without a site calibration, the default magnitude of this uncertainty component is determined by the distance between the measurement device and the turbine under test. If this distance is between 2 and 3 rotor diameters ($2D \leq \text{distance} \leq 3D$), this default magnitude is 2 % of the measured wind speed for onshore flat terrain and 1 % for offshore. If this distance is between 3 and 4 rotor diameters ($3D < \text{distance} \leq 4D$), this default magnitude is 3 % of the measured wind speed for onshore flat terrain and 2 % offshore.

In summary, the methods in this whitepaper should be applied via the uncertainty associated with measurement height, $u_{(\Delta V),measHeight}$.

7 Self-Consistency Analysis from Adjacent Bins

At the end of an evaluation, the wind speed shall be checked for consistency over the valid measurement sector. This check is an adaptation of 12-3 Section 11.3. This consistency check is to verify that although the terrain can vary and is considered complex, the wind is uniform over the measurement sector, and no additional terrain uncertainty should be considered. Figure 7-1 outlines the concept. This is completed by using the measured wind speed from the 2.5 and 3.5 rotor diameter range gates.

Figure 7-1: Terrain Variation Concept and Air Flow Change

The evaluation is as follows:

- a) Calculate a linear regression (LR) using 3.5 D as the independent variable and 2.5 D as the dependent variable for each 10° bin (j).
- b) For each 10° direction bin, calculate a predictive wind speed at 2.5 D ($v_{2.5pred,j\pm 1}$) from $v_{3.5,j}$, but using the linear regression from the adjacent (if applicable) lower (j-1) and upper (j+1) 10° direction bins. This will result in 2 calculated predictive wind speeds at 2.5 D for the j direction bin ($v_{2.5pred,j-1}$ and $v_{2.5pred,j+1}$)
 - a. For example, if the j direction bin is 290° bin, then apply the linear regression from 300° and 280° to the wind speed at 3.5 D in the 290° bin.
- c) The self-consistency parameter (SCP) is the ratio of the predicted ten-minute wind speed at 2.5 D and the measured wind speed at 2.5 D. The SCP is calculated 2 times for each 10° bin.
 - a. $SCP_{j-1} = \frac{v_{2.5pred,j-1}}{v_{2.5,j}}$
 - b. $SCP_{j+1} = \frac{v_{2.5pred,j+1}}{v_{2.5,j}}$
- d) The average of each SCP must be between 0.98 and 1.02 for no additional uncertainty to be added
- e) Repeat this for each 10° wind direction bin. Figure 7-2 outlines the concept and Table 7-1 shows an example of the output.

Figure 7-2: Wind Speed Calculation by Direction

Bin Center	SCP _{j-1}	SCP _{j+1}	Pass?
310	0.973	--	No
300	0.983	0.992	Yes
290	0.991	1.010	Yes
280	1.022	1.014	No
270	--	0.990	Yes

Table 7-1: SCP Sample Calculation Results

If one or more direction bins fails to meet the passing criteria, then the wind direction bin shall be removed or additional uncertainty applied. Uncertainty for the failed direction bin is calculated using Equation 10 from 12-3 as a reference. If both adjacent bins are outside of the limit than $u_{vt,scp,i,j}$ is an average of both terms.

$$u_{vt,scp,i,j} = \frac{|1 - SCP_{j,j-1}|}{2\sqrt{3}} \text{ OR } \frac{|1 - SCP_{j,j+1}|}{2\sqrt{3}}$$

Where

- $u_{vt,scp,i,j}$ = Is the standard uncertainty due to change in correction in wind direction bin j for wind speed bin i
- $SCP_{j,j-1}$ = Is the self-consistency parameter for wind direction j using linear regression of direction bin j-1
- $SCP_{j,j+1}$ = Is the self-consistency parameter for wind direction j using linear regression of direction bin j+1

8 Application of Simple+ Concept

In order to apply the Simple+ concept, it is important to clearly define the limitations and the envelope of applicability. A limitation to the Simple+ approach is that the wind shear measured during the pre-construction energy assessment may not be representative of the PPT location. Power curve test measurements occur at the edge of a wind farm, while preconstruction measurements are generally centrally located in the wind farm. Additionally, most wind resource masts measure wind below the hub height of modern wind turbines thus adding a vertical extrapolation uncertainty in the derived wind shear exponent. However, the latter can be mitigated with the use of a 50-2 compliant wind lidar that can measure wind shear through the rotor plane of modern wind turbines. Errors in the evaluation of the terrain suitability for Simple+ are further mitigated with the use of a 10% wind shear error safety factor. It is assumed that this should satisfactorily account for errors in horizontal (i.e. cross locations) and vertical wind shear extrapolation errors at most locations.

Errors in turbine location wind speeds estimates are less of a concern as these wind speeds should be reasonably extrapolated to the turbine location and the Simple+ terrain evaluation method is reasonably insensitive to errors in the mean wind speed at the turbine location.

For the Simple+ site suitability assessment to be valid, industry best practices for wind resources assessments should be followed with subsequent considerations:

- The turbine and preconstruction measurement locations are similar in terms of the wind regime, and any special conditions are present at the wind resource and turbine location.
- Wind speed measurements during the preconstruction phase are at least two thirds of turbine hub height.
- Wind speed measurements used to derive wind shear are following the recommended measurement heights according to 12-1 Section 7.2.8
- Wind measurements are ideally completed at or near hub height

As test sites classified solely as Simple+ have not yet been sufficiently validated for power curve testing, completing a power curve test entirely comprised of Simple+ terrain is not recommended. Until such time that this methodology has been sufficiently field tested, it is recommended that a conservative approach is taken when choosing a Simple+ candidate sites where at least three 10° valid wind direction sectors (i.e. a minimum 30° in the sector, but do not have to be consecutive) that satisfy the simple terrain criteria defined in 50-3, Section 10.4.3 are included. This approach provides a sufficiently large valid measurement sector to complete the power curve test within an acceptable

timeframe in case the Simple+ sector(s) must be excluded from the final PPT analysis. Terrain criteria defined in 50-3, Section 10.4.3.

Note that the flow described by Simple+ is overly simplified: there is no effect from friction in the treatments presented herein; the changes are only affected by changes on height; no discontinuities of the terrain are described by Simple+; and vorticities are not taken into consideration.

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10 Appendix

10.1 Simple+ Terrain Variation Equivalent Limits Derivation

$$B_{ms^{-1}} \equiv u_{\Delta V, measHeight} = \frac{\Delta V_{hor}}{\sqrt{3}}$$

$$B_{ms^{-1}} \cdot \sqrt{3} = \Delta V_{hor}$$

$$\Delta V_{hor} = V_H - V_m = V_m \left[\left(\frac{H}{H - \Delta Z} \right)^\alpha - 1 \right]$$

Therefore:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta V_{hor}}{V_m} + 1 \right)^{1/\alpha} = \frac{H}{H - \Delta Z}$$

Simplifying:

$$\Delta Z = H \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\Delta V_{hor}}{V_m} + 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \right)$$

Including the definition of $B_{\%}$:

$$\frac{B_{ms^{-1}} \cdot \sqrt{3}}{V_m} = B_{\%} \cdot \sqrt{3} = \left(\frac{H}{H + \Delta Z} \right)^\alpha - 1$$

And adding in Safety Factor (S), we have:

$$\Delta Z = H \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(B_{\%} \cdot \sqrt{3} + 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha(1+S)}}} \right)$$

For terrain variations, compute the additional allowance:

$$\Delta Z_{Simple+,TV} = H \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(B_{\%} \cdot \sqrt{3} + 1 \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha(1+S)}}} \right) + \Delta Z_{Simple,TV}$$

10.2 DEM Resources

(Retrieved from dem-world.com February 10, 2026)

Country	Data name	Resolution [m]	Format	Download link
Austria - Tirol	DGM/DOM 50cm	0.5	GeoTiff	tiris.maps.arcgis.com/ap...138
Belgium	Digital terrain model	1	GeoTiff	geo.be/catalog/de...ef9bd?!=en
Croatia	Digitalni model visina (ATOM feed)	1	TIFF+TFW	geoportal.dgu.hr/servi...n.xml
Denmark	Danmarks Højdemodel – Terræn	0.4	GeoTIFF	dataforsyningen.dk/data/930
Finland	Korkeusmalli 2 m	2	GeoTIFF	asiointi.maanm...tauslaitos.fi
France	RGE ALTI	1	ASCII Grid	geoservices.ign.fr/rgealti
Germany - Baden-Württemberg	Digitales Geländemodell - DGM1	1	XYZ	opengeodata.lgl-bw.de#/(...m1)
Germany - Bayern	Digitales Geländemodell 1m (DGM1)	1	GeoTiff	geodaten.bayern.de/open...dgm1
Germany - Berlin	Höhenlage im INSPIRE-Datenmodell (ATKIS DGM)	1	GeoTiff	gdi.berlin.de/geonet....search
Germany - Brandenburg	WCS DGM Gitterweite 1m Brandenburg mit Berlin	1	GeoTiff	
Germany - Hamburg	Digitales Höhenmodell Hamburg DGM 1	1	XYZ	metaver.de/treffera...913D5640
Germany - Hessen	Digitales Geländemodell DGM1	1	GeoTiff	gds.hessen.de/INTERS... (DGM1)
Germany - Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	INSPIRE-ATOM MV Höhe DGM	1	GeoTIFF	geoportal-mv.de/porta...e_atom
Germany - Niedersachsen	Digitales Geländemodell 1m (DGM1)	1	COG	ni-lgln-openge...ub.arcgis.com
Germany - Nordrhein-Westfalen	Digitales Geländemodell - Rasterweite 1 m	1	GeoTiff	geoportal.nrw?active...tab=map
Germany - Rheinland-Pfalz	Digitales Geländemodell 1m (DGM1)	1	GeoTiff	geoshop.rlp.de/openda...1.html

Germany - Saarland	INSPIRE SL Höhenlage-Gitter-Coverage DGM1	1	GeoTiff	geoportal.saarland.de/ma...php
Germany - Sachsen	Digitales Geländemodell 1m (DGM1)	1	XYZ	geodaten.sachsen.de/dow...html
Germany - Sachsen-Anhalt	Digitales Geländemodell (DGM)	1	GeoTiff	lvermgeo.sachsen-anhalt.de/...
Germany - Schleswig-Holstein	Digitales Geländemodell 1m (DGM1)	1		geodaten.schleswig-holstein...
Germany - Thüringen	AtomFeed Höhendaten - Digitales Geländemodell	1	GeoTiff	geoportal.thueringen.de/g...en
Luxembourg	Relevé 3D du territoire luxembourgeois (MNT)	0.5	COG	data.public.lu/fr/dat...rgeois
Netherlands	Hoogte Nederland - land - DTM	1	GeoTiff	pdok.nl/introduct...moniseerd-
Norway	Høyde DOM1	1	GeoTIFF	hoydedata.no/LaserInnsyn2
Poland	Numeryczny Model Terenu - GeoTIFF	1	GeoTIFF	mapy.geoportal.gov.pl
Scotland	The Scottish Public Sector LiDAR	1	GeoTIFF	remotesensingdata.gov.scot/...
Spain	Total ficheros Modelo Digital del Terreno – MDT02	2	COG	centrodedescargas.cnig.es/...a
Sweden	GRID	1		geotorget.lantmateriet.se/...i
Switzerland	swissALT13D	0.5	COG	swisstopo.admin.ch/en/h...ti3d
United States of America	3D Elevation Program (3DEP) 1-Meter DEM	1	GeoTIFF	apps.nationalmap.gov/dow...er/
Wales	Historic LiDAR Archive data	1	GeoTiff	datamap.gov.wales/maps...iewer